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Generation Z and Innovative Agricultural Revolution

The Generation Z or commonly called to as Gen Z, was born between the mid-1990s and early 2010s, is often characterized as the most career oriented and diverse individual because of being highly dependent on technology, associated with different perception of life fulfillment, and self-reliant and focused on personalized learning. On the other hand, agriculture is confronted with global challenges, including the need to feed a growing population, reduce the persistent levels of rural poverty, and address rising concerns about managing natural resources. The Gen Z traits play an important role in reshaping the agriculture by embracing technology, prioritizing sustainability, and fostering innovation.

The integration of technology, for instant, is driving significant change in the field of agriculture. Gen Z as raised in a digital age, is capacitated to use and develop new innovative agricultural technologies. This idea has led to the application of precise agriculture, a data-driven approach using sensor, drones, GPS, and other artificial intelligence technologies to optimize agricultural practices. The combination of remote sensing by the farmers with farm technology including gathering soil real-time condition, current crop health, and changing weather patterns can improve the farm management (Cruz et al., 2020). This technology will not only reduce the environmental footprint in agriculture, but also reduce the need for human labor, which in turn, ultimately increases productivity and revenue (Alana et al., 2020).

In addition, the Gen Z's contribution towards sustainable agriculture is not just a trend but also a necessity. This generation is deeply knowledgeable of the environmental challenges facing by the world, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, and the degradation of natural resources. Consequently, they tend to embrace sustainable practices in their agricultural approach that prioritize environmental conservation. Promoting a long-term healthy ecology rather than short-term high yields, the sustainable agricultural practices offer an economic stability for farms, and improve farmers' quality of life by solving environmental problems caused by conventional farming (Elliot 2013). Today, the Gen Z scientists, farmers, and entrepreneurs are also advocating for organic farming system, ecologically balance pest management, and creating other alternative food sources like plant-based proteins. By this, Gen Z focus on sustainability to generally ensures not only a healthy planet for the next generation but also the ability to create more profitable, resilient, and sustainable agricultural system.

Aside from technology and sustainability, Gen Z revolution in agriculture is strengthened by a deep sense of social duty. This generation believed that a responsible and sustainable agricultural future must centers on resolving issues like consuming locally produced food, food insecurity, labor rights, and equitable access to nutritious food. Some

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Gen Z farmers and organizations are now establishing and supporting community-supported agriculture (CSA), a program that gave an important opportunity for producers and farmers to develop business and marketing skills, which play a major role in the creation of more localized food systems by directly connecting farmers and consumers (Gillespie et al., 2007). Gen Z is uniquely positioned to inspire and empower people to take action towards a more sustainable food system.

Moreover, Gen Z demonstrate a strong entrepreneurial mindset. Nowadays, many young people are establishing and ventures in agricultural businesses through exploring new feasible markets and developing innovative agricultural products. Gen Z is revolutionizing the agricultural industry by harnessing the power of social media to engage with consumers, cultivate personal brands, and pioneer digital marketplaces. This entrepreneurial system of Gen Z facilitate innovation and leading the agricultural industry forward.

In conclusion, the Gen Z plays essential role in transformative modern agriculture. Their technological literacy, concern to environment, entrepreneurial mindset, and commitment towards sustainable agriculture positively reshape the landscape and future of the agriculture industry. The Gen Z contribution will undoubtedly have a remarkable and lasting change and impact on the way people produce, process, consume, and value agricultural products and foods.

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